

**ADVANCED PRACTICES ON PROVISION AND CONTROL OF
LEGISLATION ON GENERAL SECONDARY, SPECIAL SECONDARY AND
PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES**

Munira Kurbanovna Bobomarova

Independent researcher of The Supreme School OF Judges

Tel: +998 90 960 98 89

Аннотация. Мазкур мақолада умумий ўрта, ўрта махсус ва профессионал таълим муассасаларида қонунчилик ижроси устидан прокурор назоратини амалга ошириш ва бу борада хорижий давлатларнинг илғор тажрибалари тизимли-тузилмавий, қонун ҳужжатларини шарҳлаш, қиёсий-ҳуқуқий таҳлил усулларида фойдаланган ҳолда кўриб чиқилиб, тизим фаолиятини такомиллаштиришга қаратилган таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: прокурор назорати, прокуратура органлари, вояга етмаганлар, таълим муассасалари, ювенал юстиция, атторнейлик хизмати, ҳуқуқий ёрдам.

Аннотация. В статье с использованием методов системно-структурного, толкования правовых документов, сравнительно-правового анализа рассмотрены вопросы осуществления прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства в учреждениях общего среднего, среднего специального и профессионального образования и передовой опыт зарубежных стран в этом направлении, а также разработаны предложения, направленные на совершенствование деятельности системы.

Ключевые слова: прокурорский надзор, прокуратура, несовершеннолетние, образовательные учреждения, ювенальная юстиция, адвокатская служба, юридическая помощь.

Abstract. In this article, the implementation of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation in general secondary, secondary special and professional

educational institutions and the best practices of foreign countries in this regard are considered using the methods of systematic-structural, interpretation of legal documents, comparative-legal analysis, and proposals aimed at improving the system's activity are developed.

Keywords: prosecutor's supervision, prosecutor's office, minors, educational institutions, juvenile justice, attorney service, legal aid.

The protection of the rights of minors is one of the most urgent legal issues in the world community and is a component of the problems related to the protection of human rights at the centre of attention of the whole of humanity[1].

It should be noted that human rights is a concept that determines the legal status of a person in relation to the state, and describes what opportunities he has in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres [2].

As a result of the improvement of the system of protection of the rights of minors and their legal interests at the international and national levels, paying special attention to ensuring the implementation of legal acts in this area is one of the important tasks facing the prosecutor's office and other agencies. In this regard, it is important to study the advanced experience of developed foreign countries in ensuring the legal protection of minors by the prosecutor's office, in organizing control over the implementation of legislation in this field and applying their successful aspects to the national legislation and the practice of the prosecutor's control.

In this regard, juvenile justice is one of the international standards for the protection of the rights of minors through the courts.

Juvenile justice is an international term that means juvenile justice or juvenile court[3].

That is, "juvenile justice" can be called a judicial institution for minors. However, the difference between juvenile justice from the judicial body is that it is widely involved in the protection of the rights of minors in society and in solving the issues related to them. In this sense, it can be called a system of ensuring the rights of minors between the state and civil society.

For example, in the United States, France, and Japan, the juvenile justice system deals with matters such as custody, guardianship, parental sanctions, and property disputes that arise in juvenile delinquency proceedings. That is, solving civil, administrative, economic and criminal cases related to minors in these countries is within the competence of this justice. This shows that courts in developed countries are specialized and more effective experience has been accumulated. Today, specialized juvenile courts exist in more than 40 countries of the world[4].

In the experience of foreign countries, three forms of juvenile justice are widespread:

- specialized courts (USA, Bulgaria, Germany, Romania, Poland, Estonia, Lithuania, Russia, Kazakhstan, etc.);
- the executive system that has administrative powers and protects the interests of minors in the areas of criminal, family, civil, and labour law (Austria, Hungary, Spain, Latvia, Moldova, France, Japan, etc.);
- a system protecting the rights and interests of minors by courts with general jurisdiction (Belarus, Ukraine, Armenia, Kyrgyzstan, etc.) has been introduced.

The system in question has gone through a complex historical process. Historically, at first, the courts of European countries did not take into account the age of the person who committed the crime. Later, there was a tendency to focus on age and psycho-physiological development in sentencing for juvenile delinquency and delinquency. In particular, the Napoleonic Code includes the concept of "whether or not he understands the consequences of his actions" in relation to minors [5].

On July 2, 1899, in the state of Illinois, for the first time in the world, the Law "On Abandoned, Neglected and Delinquent Children and Their Care" was adopted and the juvenile court was established [6].

When talking about the experience of France in this regard, it should be noted that Ordinance No. 45-174 was adopted on February 2, 1945, on juvenile delinquents and their responsibility was established [7].

When talking about the international standards in the field of ensuring rights in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions and their specific aspects, first of all, the protection of the rights of minors is of a specific nature, which means that minors in most cases do not understand the violation of their rights and legal interests, as well as their It can be explained by the lack of independent protection from the historical development stages mentioned above.

In our opinion, the prosecutor's office in each country is established on the basis of the country's long history of development, conditions, state mechanism and socio-economic development trends in the country.

Based on the above, it is proposed to enrich Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-139 of 07.01.2008 with the following concept:

"Juvenile justice is a system of measures that includes issues of prevention of offences against them, administration of justice, social rehabilitation and integration, taking into account the characteristics of the age, gender, mental, physical and spiritual development of minors;..."

In addition, it is proposed to supplement this Law with a new Article 121:

"Article 121. Juvenile justice

1. The juvenile justice system consists of representatives of the following bodies and institutions:

- 1) Republican Commission on Juvenile Affairs;
- 2) Child rights representative;
- 3) prosecutor's office;
- 4) specialized court for juvenile cases (courts should be specialized);
- 5) internal affairs body;
- 6) health authorities;
- 7) educational institutions;
- 8) state social insurance bodies;
- 9) penal institutions;
- 10) state bodies in the field of labour, employment and migration;

- 11) state bodies in the field of probation;
- 12) local self-government body;
- 13) state and non-state centres dealing with the rights and freedoms of minors.

2. All employees working with minors must undergo special training in juvenile justice.

In fact, the analysis shows that the organization of prosecutor's offices in foreign countries and their activities are externalized based on the existing national legal system in the country.

In addition, the prosecutor's office performs its activities under one or another office or as an independent body. It should be noted that prosecutor's offices in foreign countries perform their activities according to the principle of separation of powers, either as part of the executive power, or as part of the judicial system, or without being part of any power. In this regard, A. Makhmudov expressed his opinion about the prosecutor's office under the influence of the executive authorities, according to him, "This situation does not allow to fully establish effective prosecutor's control over the activities of the law enforcement authorities[8]".

Based on the above-mentioned points, in our opinion, in implementing the best practices of developed foreign countries in the implementation of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions, the legal system, economic potential of the state, existing traditions and conditions in society and other it is desirable to take into account a number of important aspects.

The experience of developed foreign countries shows that there is no single approach to ensure legitimacy in the field of general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions.

In particular, if we look at the experience of Western countries, in most of them prosecutor's offices carry out tasks such as protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens and fighting crime in courts. In particular, the main task of the German prosecutor's office is to carry out criminal prosecution[9]. Prosecutor's office in the US

is considered an attorney's service and has no equivalent in the legal system of other countries (with the exception of Singapore), and scientists include it in the executive power system based on the theory of separation of powers [10].

However, the lack of a general control function in the prosecutor's offices of some foreign countries does not mean that prosecutor control (general control) does not exist in these countries. In particular, the main tasks performed by prosecutors at all levels in France are the supervision of criminal investigations and trials. The main task of the Prosecutor General is to exercise control over the application of criminal legislation in the entire territory under the jurisdiction of the appellate courts[11].

The Romanian Prosecutor's Office protects the common interests of the society in court and controls the legal order.

The task of the Polish Prosecutor's Office is to protect the rule of law and supervise the preliminary investigation.

The analysis shows that in the USA, Europe and other developed countries, the system of general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions is more developed, and it is appropriate to study the advanced experience of such countries.

In particular, the rights and legal interests of minors of general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions in Western European countries and the USA are protected by the juvenile justice system, a special legal branch of the state. Also, in the USA, the system of protection of the rights of minors is sufficiently organized, according to which everyone has the right to contact the relevant government agencies in connection with their suspicions that violence against children has been committed[12].

Also, the American Civil Liberties Union (ACLU): Although this organization's primary focus is not on minors of post-secondary, post-secondary, and professional education age, the ACLU advocates for the liberties and civil rights of all individuals, including minors. They work to protect youth rights and combat issues such as youth incarceration and discrimination[13].

Also, the National Center for Youth Rights (NCYL) has been established in the United States to protect the rights and civil liberties of vulnerable youth, especially child welfare and minors[14].

The Child Welfare League of America (CWLA), unlike the above-mentioned organizations, is engaged in activities to ensure the welfare and rights of children, youth and families[15].

As we mentioned above about the activities of the Youth Legal Center (YLC), it is a targeted organization created to protect the rights and freedoms of minors in court[16].

The Children's Defense Fund (CDF) is one of the largest organizations in the United States dedicated to protecting the rights of all children, especially children from low-income families and children with disabilities[17].

Additionally, the National Association of Children's Counsel (NACC) is an organization of legal professionals dedicated to promoting the rights of children and families in the legal system and ensuring that children have adequate representation in legal matters[18].

Protection of the freedoms and civil rights of minors, protection of the welfare of young people in need of protection, especially the welfare of children, and protection of the rights and civil liberties of minors, children, young people and ensuring the well-being and rights of families, protecting the rights and freedoms of minors in court, protecting the rights of children, especially from low-income families and children with disabilities, and providing legal assistance to minors as the main activities of the prosecutor's office.

In addition, based on the comprehensiveness of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation in the field of minors and the volume of work to be carried out, as well as the insufficient number of employees of the prosecutor's office directly carrying out activities in this area, in order to increase the effectiveness of the prosecutor's control in this direction, the existing 9 - it is appropriate to give the

network the status of "department" based on the scope of their work, creating additional staff units in the region.

Also, the structures of the General Prosecutor's Office and regional prosecutor's office provide direct assistance in developing plans for providing "legal assistance" regarding issues related to the rights and freedoms of minors, and in improving the mechanisms of pre-trial resolution of the case.

As a continuation of the above, it should be noted that "Hotlines[19]" have been launched in the Russian Federation in order to protect the rights and interests of children. According to the "Code of the Rights of the Child" of Georgia, hotlines for reporting violence against children have been established in pre-school and public education and professional education organizations. Also, calls on any issues related to the violation of children's rights are received and reported by the Office of the Public Defender of Georgia through a special hotline that operates continuously (24/7)[20].

Unfortunately, information from the organizations "Childsafe Movement[21]" and "Child Helpline International[22]" confirm that there are no hotlines for the protection of children's rights in our country.

According to him, about 40 European countries such as Germany, Belgium, Cyprus, Croatia, Estonia, Poland, Sweden, Finland, and Slovenia, more than 30 Asian countries such as China, South Korea, India, Indonesia, Iran, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, as well as Botswana, Cameroon, Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda, Togo, and more than 30 African countries have established hotlines for the protection of children's rights.

In our opinion, it is necessary to establish special structures aimed at protecting the rights of minors in general secondary, secondary and professional educational institutions in our country and introduce a hotline for the protection of minors' rights. In particular, the system that receives through the "Childcare" system and implements the necessary urgent measures should be received directly by the employees who perform this activity, and the received appeals should be immediately sent to the competent state office. Based on the socio-psychological aspects of minors, the

composition of these structures should be appointed not from teachers, but from representatives of the specialty of psychologists. After all, we learned from the results of the research that cases of violations of the rights of minors are committed by the employees and administrations of educational institutions in these institutions.

This is important in identifying, eliminating and preventing violated rights in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions.

In addition, it helps the prosecutor's office in the implementation of prosecutor's supervision in the field of minors. That is, any news and information about violations affecting the rights and legal interests of minors will have a positive effect on the prompt prosecution of the prosecutor's office on these issues and the early elimination of violations.

As proof of our point, the official website of the US Department of Education has created an opportunity to report violations of the law, whose homepage states that "No one shall ever be subject to reprisals or threats of retaliation for reporting violations of the law involving the funds, programs, or operations of the US Department of Education." should not be done. "Federal laws protect the rights and freedoms of employees of certain organizations that receive government funds, as well as the privacy of personal information of individuals who disclose information they reasonably believe has been wrongdoing and who are subsequently subject to adverse action."

In addition, if we look at the French experience, the prosecutor's office in France operates within the courts and is managed by the minister of justice. In particular, prosecutor's offices have broad powers to protect the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens in the criminal, civil and administrative spheres. The role of the prosecutor in civil proceedings is determined by the importance of his functions, which is primarily reflected in the control of the legality of the decisions made by the courts, and the protection of the rights of the disabled and minors. It should be noted that according to French law, the participation of the prosecutor in cases such as adoption,

determination and change of custody and guardianship of minors is defined as mandatory[23].

In addition, in France, prosecutors play a crucial role in ensuring legitimacy in the education sector, including general secondary, secondary specialized and vocational education. Their duties are primarily aimed at investigating and prosecuting violations of laws and regulations related to education.

When it comes to education, prosecutors can be involved in a variety of scenarios, such as:

1. Protection of minors: If there are cases of physical or mental abuse, neglect or any form of harm to students in educational institutions, prosecutors can intervene.
2. Academic integrity: They may conduct investigations into cases of academic dishonesty, cheating or fraud during examinations or assessments.
3. Safety: Prosecutors will take action against illegal activities, violence or any threats on school premises that may threaten the safety of students, teachers or staff.
4. Compliance with Education Laws: They ensure that educational institutions comply with regulations related to curricula, qualifications and certifications.
5. Dealing with Discrimination or Harassment: Prosecutors handle cases of discrimination, harassment, or any violation of student rights in the educational setting.

In addition, prosecutors in the country can conduct investigative actions to gather evidence when suspected violations come to their attention, and if there is sufficient evidence, they can charge them and take the case to court. In court, they present evidence, represent the state's interests, and demand appropriate legal measures or penalties against those responsible.

It should be noted that the education system in France is primarily overseen by the Ministry of National Education, and prosecutors work with education authorities to ensure that laws and regulations are properly enforced.

Also, in the Eastern countries, the tasks performed by the prosecutor's office are different, and their special importance is to ensure legality in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions.

In particular, the prosecutor's office in Japan is organizationally part of the Ministry of Justice and operates based on the principle of a single system.

Also, according to Article 14 of the Law on Public Prosecutions of Japan, the Minister of Justice can exercise general control over prosecutors in their duties... However, in relation to the investigation and consideration of certain cases, it is the authority of the Prosecutor General only.

Therefore, compared to other Asia-Pacific countries, their supervisory powers are quite limited and only supervise the investigation of crimes and the execution of sentences imposed by the courts. It should be noted that special attention is paid to the protection of the rights of minors and their social protection by the state in Japan. According to A.N. Larin and I.N. Konoplevoy, "In Japan, the priority form of placement of children left without parental care is placement in orphanages, and family forms of placement are rarely used, which is undoubtedly an expression of confidence in state care."

From the above, it can be concluded that according to the legislation of these countries, although there is no control over the implementation of legislation among the tasks performed by the prosecutor's office, in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions, compliance with laws, ensuring legality, and most importantly, protecting the rights of minors, their social welfare by the state the system of providing protection is developing. Based on the results of the research, when studying the real essence of this situation, we can see in the example of Japan that as the countries develop economically, socially and spiritually, there is no need for separate control bodies.

As proof of our opinion, Japan was strongly influenced by the Chinese legal system from the 7th century, and the number of strong control structures in the country was not inferior to that of many countries. In 1890, Japan adopted the Meiji Constitution under the influence of Germany. After the defeat in World War II, Japan has been under the influence of the laws of the United States of America since 1947 and has been implementing this Constitution without any changes. However, unlike

the US Constitution, Articles 31-40 include or strengthen a number of provisions related to human rights in criminal cases.

At the same time, one of the models formed in the world based on the tasks of prosecutor's offices is the organization of control over the implementation of legislation. The analysis shows that, unlike the Western countries, in most countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, such as Russia, Kazakhstan, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan, one of the main tasks of the prosecutor's office is the institution of prosecutorial control over the implementation of legislation.

Therefore, it is important to study the advanced experience and successful aspects of these countries in organizing the prosecutor's control over the execution of laws in the field of minors, analyze the existing problems and shortcomings, and improve the prosecutor's control in this field in our country. For example, one of the main tasks of the prosecutor's office is to organize control over the implementation of legislation on minors in the Russian Federation. For example, departments for working with minors and young people operate in prosecutor's offices of a number of subjects of the Federation (in Tula, Saratov, Voronezh and other regional prosecutor's offices). Also, the activities of the prosecutor's office in the field of legal protection of minors are of particular importance. In particular, at the initiative of the prosecutor's offices of Volgograd, Kursk regions, and Sevastopol cities, regional regulatory documents that limit the rights of citizens regarding monthly payments for their children aged 3 to 7 years or do not fully regulate their provision have been adapted to the federal legislation. It should be noted that in the Russian Federation, the most basic legal document regulating the prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions is the Law of the Russian Federation "On the Prosecutor's Office" and the Decree of the Prosecutor General of the Federation dated 13.12.2021 "Legislation on Juveniles", the order No. 744 on the organization of the prosecutor's control over the observance of their rights and legal interests.

It is noteworthy that the organization of the prosecutor's supervision in this field covers almost all relations related to minors, which can be seen in the supervision of compliance with the legislation on protection from information harmful to children's health, status, moral and spiritual development. In particular, according to the order of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Russian Federation dated 13.12.2021 No. 744 "On the organization of prosecutorial control over the observance of the legislation on minors, their rights and legal interests", the implementation of legislation on protection from information harmful to children's health and development One of the main tasks of the prosecutor's office is to carry out systematic control over the information, limit the use of such information in the prescribed manner and hold the persons guilty of its dissemination to legal responsibility.

Today, along with the development of the world information network, its harmful elements can affect the future of our youth and the development of the country.

In this regard, O.S. Kapinus said that "at the initiative of the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Tatarstan, a special system "Fighting Offenses on the Internet" was created and implemented, which automatically identifies web pages with prohibited content in real-time and sends them to Roskomnadzor for blocking. if there is, it allows you to create documents to send to the court. The peculiarity of the system is that it detects not only extremism but also fourteen categories of prohibited information, such as drugs, child suicide, gambling, and child pornography.

Also, as information, in 2017-2018, the game called "Blue Whale", which propagates evil and violence, spread over the Internet and became widespread. In 2017, it was found that among the students of 31 schools and 5 colleges in Tashkent, there were those who played this game. At the same time, one-third of Internet users are children under the age of 18. In such a case, it was found that there are 9 thousand sites promoting easy ways to commit suicide and more than 4 thousand sites with sexual content on the global network.

As a confirmation of our opinion, EUROSTAT, the statistical office of the European Union, is one of the most prominent statistical organizations that collect data

on crime rates, criminal justice, including juvenile crime statistics, according to the most recent data published by it, it provided data in 26 EU countries. 14 of the country's police-recorded fraud cases totalled 2,450,800, an increase of 4 per cent over the previous year. Most of the fraud crimes reported in this category are cybercrime cases committed by young people.

After all, the issues related to the study of the implementation of legislation in this direction by the prosecutor's office, the implementation of inspections are included in the order of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 139 "On improving the effectiveness of control activities over the implementation of legislation on minors", as well as the unified reporting portal of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan ("P" form) was not reflected in the control table over the implementation of legislation on minors.

In addition, order No. 228 of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the regulation of the Department of Supervision over the Juvenile Law Enforcement of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on May 25, 2021. In the "Regulation on the Control Department" one of the main tasks of the department should be defined as control over the implementation of legislation aimed at protecting minors from information harmful to their health.

Based on the above analysis, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Children's Rights"

In Article 4, the protection of children from information harmful to their health should be defined as the main direction of the state policy on the protection of children's rights.

Also, it is proposed to add a separate Article 161 to this Law entitled "Guarantee of protection of the child from information that negatively affects his health" and to state it in the context of "the state guarantees the protection of children from information that harms their physical, mental and social health". will be done.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to study the issues of introducing the juvenile justice system in developed foreign countries in our country based on our national legislation, the existing legal system and a number of other important factors.

Studies show that the juvenile justice system has developed in many foreign countries, and this institution has had a positive effect in protecting the rights of minors, preventing offences between them, and also in bringing them to justice for crimes committed by them.

For information, according to the results of the international index published by the International Network of Children's Rights, the Republic of Uzbekistan occupies 112th place out of 197 countries with a score of 42.9. According to the results of the international assessment, although our country has ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the fact that the "juvenile justice" system has not been fully incorporated into the national legislation has been pointed out as a shortcoming.

We believe that the reflection of this system in national legislation will serve as a basis for improving our position in international indexes.

In conclusion, it is important to improve our national legislation by using the advanced experiences of developed foreign countries in protecting the rights and legal interests of minors, supporting them socially, as well as implementing prosecutorial supervision in this field, thereby increasing the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision of prosecutorial authorities. is enough.

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